

THE IMPACT OF NIGHTSHIFT ON THE PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PHYSICAL HEALTH OF WORKERS IN US IT STAFFING INDUSTRY IN TIRUNELVELI DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT:

Being one of the top outsourcing locations in the world offers many advantages for India. Although the rise of outsourcing to India obviously has a positive effect on our culture and economy, this study discusses the impact of nightshift on the psychological and physical health of workers with respect to the US IT Staffing Industry. As the US IT Staffing Industry is a relatively new industry in India, there are only a handful of night shift studies and their effect on the health of workers in the industry. Numerous studies have been conducted on the health of night shift employees in other occupations, such as nurses, health workers, petrochemical workers, truck drivers and factory workers. Staffing Industry is often emphasized as more stressful than other comparable forms of employment. This encourages current research to add to established information on the specifics of the Staffing Industry, with a particular emphasis on the impact of night shift work on the health of employees in the US IT Staffing Industry.

The broad objective of the study is to study the impact of night shift work on the psychological and physical health of workers in US IT Staffing Industry in Tirunelveli district. The specific objectives are to examine the industry specific impact and problems on employees in Tirunelveli; to explore the implications of the nightshift job on the physical and psychological health of the employees in US IT Staffing Industry in Tirunelveli; to explore for any difference of impact in males and females and to offer suggestions based on the findings of the study. This study used a descriptive research design, which is a quantitative research method. The questionnaires were distributed, and the data was analysed statistically.

KEYWORDS: Impact of Nightshift, Psychological Health, Physical Health, IT Workers, IT Staffing Industry

INTRODUCTION

In a country like India, the rise of outsourcing has had a significant economic impact. India has emerged as one of the most favoured outsourcing destinations due to numerous advantages such as world-class intellectual and internet resources, low-cost infrastructure, multilingual capabilities, and so on. India has emerged as the tech powerhouse of the twenty-first century, providing a wide range of services, including IT allow services (ITES) and Business Process Outsourcing (BPO).

Outsourcing, or handing over certain information management and processing resources to a third party, has recently piqued the interest of both information systems and corporate executives. With rising cost pressures, management sees outsourcing as a viable choice for better leveraging capital, controlling costs, and concentrating on strategic and value-added activities. The trend towards global outsourcing (i.e., selectively transferring certain functions to a subcontractor) of information services can be traced mainly to two factors: cost reduction pressure and advancements in information technology. In the face of increasing pressure to reduce costs, an increasing number of U.S. companies are finding the possibility of global outsourcing of information services quite attractive, given that wage rates in many underdeveloped and newly industrialised countries are significantly lower than those in the United States (Hamilton 1988). In recent years, the number of outsourcing vendors in the United States has risen dramatically, owing to the relocation of white-collar jobs in the service sector to other countries.

US OUTSOURCING IN INDIA

One of the key factors for interest in international outsourcing is the substantial difference in staff pay levels between developed and developing countries. Outsourcing of software development activities is also a limited but growing trend. India's distinct advantages in this regard are the availability of very low wages and a large number of English-speaking, technically qualified graduates (approximately a quarter million new professional graduates each year) (Hazarika 1991; Senn 1991).

The staffing industry in India has grown from a sleepy \$100 million industry to a \$6 billion industry in the last 18 years. Over this time period, the Staffing Industry has expanded due to shorter tenures of senior executives, numerous work openings for junior executives, and the advent of new sunrise industries such as Insurance, Telecom, and Ecommerce. High-skilled industries, such as IT and engineering, have relied heavily on workers outsourcing to meet their cyclical needs.

Tirunelveli is the study place for this study. According to anecdotal data and primary research, there are four US IT Staffing companies in Tirunelveli with 85 employees, 66% male and 34% female.

The US IT Staffing companies that have been set up in India are offshoring businesses, which means that" the parent company is situated in another country or continent. This implies that normal business hours of the parent company and the offshore businesses are at different time.

Shift work refers to hours of work that occur beyond the normal daily schedule, i.e. work times that do not fall between 6 a.m. and 6 p.m. Alert and output of shift workers, particularly when night shift work schedules can be compromised. Night employees and shift workers are at an elevated risk of falling asleep at work and falling asleep while driving home after work (Novak and Auvil-Novak 1996).

Shift work has been described as an emerging risk factor for a number of medical and mental health conditions (Scott 2016).

NIGHTSHIFT WORK AND HEALTH

The natural clock of the body, or the circadian rhythm, is such that it is programmed to stay up and work during the day and to rest well at night. A number of diseases have been empirically related to nightshift function. Disruption of circadian rhythms (leading to sleep/wake disturbances, desynchronisation of internal processes, and increased disease susceptibility); disturbed socio-temporal patterns (resulting from atypical work hours, leading to family problems, reduced social support, and stress); and unfavourable changes in healthy behaviours are all linked to shift work and disease (Bøggild and Knutsson 1999:85–99).

Psychological health refers to how people think about their lives in general and in certain domains, as well as how they feel about them, based on their own ethical expectations. Disorientation, indecisiveness, inability to focus, battling intrusive impulses, restless mind, and so on have become commonplace.

In many psychological and physiological facets, sleep plays a fundamental restorative and developmental function, and quality sleep is a must for optimal health. An adequate amount of sleep is essential for the control of body metabolism and the preservation of a high quality of life. Previous study has attributed low sleep quality and length to behavioural and physiological disorders caused by changes in the endocrine and immune systems.

During the night shift, time for rest and sleep is transferred to working hours, which is one of the most important sources of circadian cycle disturbance, resulting in major changes in sleep and 20 biological functions that can impair physical and psychological well-being and adversely influence work efficiency.

There are questions about this workplace's psychological susceptibility to stress and burnout. Organizations in India are also concerned about high turnover rates, absenteeism, and occupational diseases, implying that psychosocial aspects among workers should be examined more closely. There has been no empirical study on job stress, health problems, and burnout among workers in the US IT industry in India.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Pati, Parganiha, and Reinberg 2001 Shift employment has a number of negative consequences, including an increased risk of workers developing a variety of physical and mental health problems, trouble managing work and personal life, and poor interactions with family members, all of which can negatively impact children's social and academic growth. The failure of the employee to adjust to the shift work routine will result in a loss of physical and psychological health, as well as negative safety and efficiency effects.

Ferri et al. 2016 The night shift, in particular, is one of the most common causes of circadian rhythm disturbance, resulting in major changes in sleep and biological functions that can influence physical and psychological well-being as well as negatively impact work efficiency. In contrast to day shift employees, they recorded the lowest mean score in the items of job satisfaction, quality and 28 quantity of sleep, as well as more frequent chronic fatigue, psychological, and cardiovascular symptoms.

According to **Burdalak et al. 2012 and Moon et al. 2016**, night shift healthcare staff have a 1.4-fold higher risk of subclinical hypothyroidism than day shift workers with age-adjusted TSH levels. It is possible that night shift-induced changes in sleep schedule, timing, and quality can disrupt the body's normal circadian rhythm, resulting in abnormal TSH secretion. (Leso et al. 2020)

Chunlin Li et al. 2021 Excessive computer use has been linked to both tension and migraine headaches. Computer use is particularly popular among IT staff, who use computers for work, school, and recreation.

According to a study by **Yong, Li, and Calvert 2017**, night shift employees were the most likely to have these sleep issues. Short sleep time, poor sleep quality, impaired ADL score, and insomnia were discovered to be widespread among US employees, especially night shift workers. Furthermore, night shift employees were at a greater risk for all of these sleep disorders, and these higher risks continued even after controlling for possible confounders such as extended 33 work hours (48 hours/week), sociodemographic features, and health/lifestyle/work factors. This tension can contribute to physical health problems like insomnia, psychological health issues like depression, lifestyle issues like alcohol and opioid use, and interpersonal conflicts.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The Indian outsourcing sector is bolstered by a strong pro-IT government whose strategies on the economy, GDP growth, taxation, power, telecom, industrial parks, and special zones have aided in the development of infrastructure and communications systems. The Indian economy is growing at a rapid pace, thanks to the growth of the outsourcing industry in India, especially from the United States. Other urban and regional cities like Tirunelveli, in addition to metropolitan cities, prosper from the abundance of graduates with strong communication skills.

Nevertheless, numerous observations in the preceding chapter and a review of the literature above show that the problems related to the physical and psychological health of nightshift workers, especially in the IT Staffing industry, have not been thoroughly investigated by skilled social workers in India. Multiple surveys have been undertaken on the problems facing nightshift jobs in healthcare, manufacturing, mines, call centres, and so on, but there is a lack of research on the IT Staffing Industry in terms of their physical and psychological health. This research, in this opinion, is an effort to fill the void by analysing the physical and psychological health of nightshift employees in the US IT Staffing Industry. Hence, the problem for investigation is termed: “A Study on The Impact of Nightshift on the Psychological and Physical Health of Workers in US IT Staffing Industry in Tirunelveli District”.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

As the US IT Staffing Industry is a relatively new industry in India, there are only a handful of night shift studies and their effect on the health of workers in the industry. Numerous studies have been conducted on the health of night shift employees in other occupations, such as nurses, health workers, petrochemical workers, truck drivers and factory workers. Staffing Industry is often emphasized as more stressful than other comparable forms of employment. This encourages current research to add to established information on the specifics of the Staffing Industry, with a particular emphasis on the impact of night shift work on the health of employees in the US IT Staffing Industry.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

India has had a lot to benefit from being one of the world's largest outsourcing destinations. Although the rise of outsourcing to India obviously has a positive effect on our culture and economy, this study discusses only the negative aspects of working in the night shift with respect to the US IT Staffing Industry.

As the US IT Staffing Industry is a relatively new industry in India, there are only a handful of night shift studies and their effect on the health of workers in the industry. Numerous studies have been conducted on the health of night shift employees in other occupations, such as nurses, health workers, petrochemical workers, truck drivers and factory workers. Staffing Industry is often emphasized as more stressful than other comparable forms of employment. This encourages current research to add to established information on the specifics of the Staffing Industry, with a particular emphasis on the impact of night shift work on the health of employees in the US IT Staffing Industry. This study will be undertaken to find out the

impact of night shift work on the psychological and physical health of workers in US IT Staffing Industry in Tirunelveli district.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The broad objective of the study is to study the impact of night shift work on the psychological and physical health of workers in US IT Staffing Industry in Tirunelveli district.

The specific objectives are as follows:

- I. To examine the industry specific impact and problems on employees in Tirunelveli.
- II. To explore the implications of the nightshift job on the physical and psychological health of the employees in US IT Staffing Industry in Tirunelveli.
- III. To explore for any difference of impact in males and females
- IV. To offer suggestions based on the findings of the study

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research area is the Tirunelveli district in the Indian state of Tamil Nadu. The universe of the study includes all the nightshift workers in US IT Staffing Industry of Tirunelveli district in Tamil Nadu. The selection of the area was the first step. The selection of the district was accomplished using purposive sampling. Tirunelveli district was selected purposefully for the convenience of the study since the researcher has 5+ years of experience working in the district in US IT Staffing Industry. The selection of employees was the second step. There are 85 nightshift employees specifically working in US IT Staffing Industry in Tirunelveli district. All the employees were contacted for the survey, out of which 19 did not respond, 9 of them worked for less than 6 months in nightshift and 57 respondents were selected out of the 85 employees.

Data were collected through personal interviews with senior managers of IT Staffing Companies in Tirunelveli district to acquire the population of IT Staffing professionals working in the industry as night shift workers and the male-female ratio.

The US IT Staffing industry in India has emerged only in the last decade or so and is still growing rapidly. Since outsourcing of US IT Staffing industry is a new and developing trend, little is known about the health problems that are unique to this industry. Since no specific scale has been developed or standardized for night shift workers in this industry, General Health Scale from Business Process Outsourcing Shiftwork Rating Scale (BPO-SRS)(Solomon n.d.) is used to analyse physical health. For psychological health, GHQ-12 was used.

The completed questionnaires were exported into MS Excel database. Categorical variables were reported as absolute and percentage frequencies. A descriptive stage characterized working population and their health status. In addition, bar graphs and pie diagrams were also plotted to present some descriptive statistics. Associations between nightshift work and

physical health were studied as well as the relationship between nightshift work and psychological distress.

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study used a descriptive research design, which is a quantitative research method. Descriptive research entails collecting data that illustrates activities, then organising, tabulating, depicting, and describing the information gathered (Glass and Hopkins 1984). It also employs visual aids including graphs and charts to help the reader comprehend the data distribution. Since the human mind is incapable of fully comprehending a vast amount of raw data, descriptive statistics are critical in reducing the data to a manageable format. There was no manipulation of the input variables and there was no control or experimental group. The questionnaires were distributed, and the data was analysed statistically.

FINDINGS

The following conclusions could be drawn from the findings of this study:

More than half of the respondents self-assessed their health status and rated that they have

Health problems experiencing after working in nightshift

US IT Staffing employees who fully completed the GHQ questionnaire, 9 (16%) showed a moderate (classic GHQ score 3–5) and 36 (63%) showed high (equal to or greater than 6) level of psychological distress, as shown in Figure. The median GHQ score was 7; the mean was 7.02. On the Likert method, 28 (49%) of employees had scores greater than 12, corresponding to possible psychological distress, and 16 (28%) scores greater than 20, corresponding to severe psychological distress. The median Likert score was 19, and the mean 19.67. For women, the mean score was 19.33 with a standard deviation of 4.8, compared to mean score of 18.18 (SD 3.33). 5.1.4 ANALYTICAL STEP 21%

The high incidence (79% in bi-modal and 77% in Likert score) of moderate to severe psychological disorders (GHQ score equal to or greater than 3) is in agreement with existing research that establishes a strong correlation between nightshift work and psychological health.

The high incidence of physical ailments, viz. Headaches, poor digestion, back pain, neck pain among the population studied are in agreement with existing research pertaining to call centre employees and BPOs.

SUGGESTIONS

Other concerns that need to be studied further in order to ascertain the true effect of nightshift work and stress on the physical and psychological wellbeing of workers were discovered as a result of the present research. In future studies, using comprehensive qualitative methods such as in-depth interviews will aid in the identification of new and relevant variables (which were not accounted for in the measures used in the current study). Furthermore, due to the study's time constraint, only Tirunelveli was taken into account. A larger sample size may be used in future studies, allowing for further subject comparisons. Age, gender, marital status, job title and salary were only a few of the demographic variables considered in the analysis to characterise the sample. Future studies should concentrate on these factors and their potential impact on person expectations of quality of life.

LIMITATIONS

In India, industry norms do not adequately characterise the IT staffing industry. Some IT (Software Development) businesses provide IT Staff Augmentation, whilst others incorporate as consultancy agencies which could cover a number of industries. Obtaining empirical data on the Indian market was difficult due to the lack of a given classification. As a result, anecdotal facts and secondary data were used. The questionnaires themselves, researchers' use of the questionnaires, and individuals' responses to the questionnaires are all possible limitations of using self-report questionnaires to study the effects of nightshift jobs.

Participants' self-reports were used to assess physical and psychological health. Because of social desirability and memory biases, self-report tests are vulnerable to inaccuracy. Despite the differences between self-reported wellbeing and people's actual health, self-reported health is also considered a reliable measure of health in a variety of social contexts.

CONCLUSION

This study made on the physical and psychological impact of night shift work has found that regular and continuous employment on nightshifts is detrimental to the worker's welfare, especially in matters pertaining to their social life, family life and health. To elaborate upon the detrimental health consequences, the cross-sectional study of 57 US IT staffing workers in Tirunelveli district has shown that physical pain (musculoskeletal conditions, auditory or visual 71 fatigue) was the most identified ailment by nightshift workers followed by gastrointestinal problems. Psychological distress was common among the selected sample of nightshift workers.

Thus, the higher vulnerability of the US IT industry regular nightshift workers to physical as well as mental health problems merit extra care and routine health check-ups. Further research is required so as to quantify the extent of damage to the health of the worker and recommend sustainable solutions to the same. A human centric policy needs to be adopted by the organisations that put employee welfare at the core along with business interests for a sustainable, safe and healthy work environment.

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